

**SOCIAL MEDIA LANGUAGE AND TERMINOLOGY: EVOLUTION AND IMPACT
ON COMMUNICATION**

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Annotation. This article examines the language of social media as a dynamic and informal communication system that reflects changes in society and cultural trends. It focuses on the specific features of the language, such as the use of abbreviations, emojis, and borrowed terms. The article discusses key concepts, including hashtags, likes, trends, and memes, which have become part of everyday communication. It also analyzes the impact of the language of social media on user identity and intergenerational interactions, as well as the challenges associated with misunderstandings and the spread of misinformation. The article highlights the importance of studying the language of social media to understand its role in modern society and find solutions to emerging challenges.

Keywords: term, social network terminology, language, society, communication, linguistic culture, communication

Introduction

With the advancement of technology and the proliferation of social media, not only has the way we communicate changed, but so has the language we use. The language of social media is a dynamic system that reflects societal changes, cultural trends, and new forms of interaction. In this article, we will explore the characteristics of the language of social media, its terminology, and its impact on everyday communication.

1. Features of the language of social networks

The language of social media is characterized by a number of specific features that distinguish it from traditional language. Firstly, it is often informal and conversational. Users tend to use abbreviations, emojis, and slang, which makes communication easier and more relaxed. For example, instead of using the full expression "thank you," you may see the abbreviation "thx," and instead of using "good," you may see "ok."

Secondly, the language of social media actively borrows elements from other languages and cultures. Globalization and the availability of information contribute to the mixing of languages and the emergence of new terms. For example, the words "selfie" and "hashtag" have become part of everyday communication in many countries.

Thirdly, the language of social media is subject to rapid change. New terms and phrases emerge and disappear at an astonishing pace, depending on current events, memes, and trends. This creates a unique linguistic environment where users must stay up-to-date with the latest changes in order to communicate effectively.

2. Social media terminology

Social media terminology includes many new words and expressions that have become part of everyday usage. Let's explore some of the most common terms:

A hashtag (#) is a word or phrase that precedes the # symbol and is used to group messages under a specific topic. Hashtags allow users to find content related to their interests and participate in discussions.

Like (from the English word "like") is a feature that allows users to express approval or interest in content. Likes have become an important indicator of the popularity of publications and influence the algorithms that display content in news feeds.

A trend is a topic or hashtag that becomes popular at a certain point in time. Trends can be related to events, memes, or cultural phenomena, and they often reflect public sentiment.

A follower (from the English "follower") is a user who is subscribed to another user's updates on a social network. The number of followers is often considered as an indicator of a person's popularity or influence on the network.

A meme is a cultural element that spreads online, often in the form of an image with text. Memes can be humorous or satirical and can quickly become viral.

3. The impact of social media language on communication

The language of social media has a significant impact on users' everyday communication. Firstly, it contributes to the creation of new forms of communication, such as memes and visual content. This allows users to convey emotions and ideas more effectively.

Secondly, the language of social media influences the formation of users' identities. People use specific terms and communication styles to create a self-image on the internet, which can reflect their interests, values, and belonging to certain groups.

Thirdly, the use of social media language can lead to misunderstandings between generations. Young people who actively use social media may use terms and expressions that are not always clear to older generations. This can create barriers in communication and lead to conflicts.

4. Problems and Challenges

One of the main issues is the potential for misunderstandings due to the informal nature of communication. The use of abbreviations and slang can lead to confusion and misinterpretation of messages.

Additionally, social media language can contribute to the spread of misinformation.

The rapid dissemination of information without fact-checking can result in the creation of false news and panic among users.

Finally, the use of social media language can have a negative impact on users' literacy.

The frequent use of abbreviations and informal language can lead to a decline in language culture and writing skills.

Conclusion

The language of social media is a unique and dynamic system that reflects changes in society and culture. The terminology of social media is constantly evolving, incorporating new words and expressions that become part of everyday communication. However, this evolution also presents challenges, such as misunderstandings and the spread of misinformation.

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